

THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL NOISELESSNESS IN ACTIVATING AND SUSTAINING MARKET PRIORITY IN COMPANIES CASE STUDY OF A MECHANICAL INDUSTRIES ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the characteristics that contribute to organizational noiselessness, as well as their implications for organizational market priority. The mechanical Industries Corporation has been chosen to comprehend the reality of organizational noiselessness and to analyze what is required in order to make the necessary recommendations in order to maintain the corporation's Market priority while also reducing the phenomenon of organizational noiselessness and its impact.

1. Methodology

1.1. Research Question

The phenomenon of organizational noiselessness in organizing, particularly if we know that the management process is centered on personnel. Without effective and competent individuals who can aid the company in reaching its desired goal, no organization, regardless of size or competency, can achieve the aim to which it strives. This is because, regardless of size or skills, an organization's capacity to achieve its goals or be successful is not exclusively dependent on management's efforts; people play an important role as well. While these individuals or employees may have a range of attitudes, some are hostile to the company's working practices and processes. Others, on the other hand, maintain their composure and refrain from criticizing their employer or coworkers. In many of our organizations, this is true, which means there is a lack of organizational noiselessness, which leads to a variety of unwanted phenomena such as low organizational loyalty, organizational terrorism, and a reduction in worker morale, all of which are bad to the company. After learning more about the impact of organizational noiselessness on market advantage, we decided to investigate it further. As a result, the primary focus of the research was on identifying organizational noiselessness and its implications for possible market advantage, which could be measured using the following questions:

1. What is the researched organization's organizational noiselessness scale?
2. What is the size of the possible market advantage?
3. What is the source of the organizational noiselessness that exists in the organization in order of perceived importance, from the standpoint of the research sample?
4. What's the link between organizational noiselessness, its causes, and the potential for a competitive advantage?
5. How does the absence of organizational noise affect the chances of acquiring a competitive advantage?

1.2. The Purpose of the Study

The study set intended to accomplish the following goals:

1. In research, the mutable s are specified.
2. Determining what motivates individuals to use organizational noiselessness in the workplace.
3. Determine the company's market priority as well as the level of organizational noiselessness.

1.3. Hypotheses for Research

The following important assumptions and assumptions underpin the research:

The first key assumption is that the reasons of organizational noiselessness and the likelihood of gaining a competitive advantage are inversely related. The following assumptions were made based on the fundamental premise:

The first sub-assumption is that organizational noiselessness and strategic cost leadership have a significant adverse relationship.

The second sub-assumption is that the reasons of organizational noiselessness and the strategic positioning of the product are very inversely related.

Organizational noiselessness and strategic attention are significantly inversely connected, according to the third sub-assumption.

The second fundamental premise is that organizational noiselessness (and its causes) have a significant negative influence on the potential for market advantage. The following assumptions were made based on the fundamental premise:

The first sub-assumption is that corporate silence is detrimental to cost leadership strategies.

The second sub-assumption is that organizational noiselessness (and the factors that contribute to it) has a negative impact on product strategy.

The last sub-assumption is that organizational noiselessness (and its causes) reduce strategic attention.

1.4 Research instruments and mutable

The study includes the following variable:

- 1- Organizational noiselessness is a distinct quality that is researched and quantified in terms of the reasons for it, the instruments used to test it, and the number of items in each of them.
- 2- The probable Market priority is the dependent variable that is studied utilizing the Market priority strategic, which is the dimension that must be quantified.

2. Theoretical Underpinnings

2.1 Quietness in the workplace

Organizational noiselessness is viewed as a goal having a clear impact on the many development processes and difficulties that organizations face since it has a substantial impact on efficiency and impactiveness. Since it is linked to employee behavior, particularly negative behavior, and it represents one of the primary challenges in the growth and advancement process, there has been an increase in interest in that object. Human resources are the most crucial players in every business. The transformation process. As a result, an organization's success and efficiency are determined by its people capital. In today's firms, employees who can share their ideas, attitudes, abilities, and expertise in a safe and productive environment are necessary. There are times, though, when employees have essential ideas for the organization but choose not to share them, causing problems for the company. One of the main causes of change management program failure and one of the biggest impediments to growth in any institution is a lack of information, which Moris and Milliken refer to as "organizational noiselessness." As a result of increased competition among organizations, high customer expectations in I in s, and a str in g focus on quality, organizations now have higher expectations in I in s such as taking the initiative, talking, and taking responsibility for employees in order to ensure that they will stay on the job (Shirvani et al., 2019).

Various conceptions and definitions of the thing were associated with it, depending on one's point of view. In that study, we'll try to address some of them in order to find commonalities that we may apply in our research. Organizational noiselessness is a culture that penetrates the entire organization, not a personality trait. It refers to an individual's or a group's general attitude toward organizational issues. Although noiselessness is a process, it has a detrimental impact on some parts of business and is a favored form of communication among employees. This is significant since upward information flow has been found to be important and beneficial in every investigation. To put it another way, organizational noiselessness isn't always seen as a passive trait because it can be active. It should be a visible, conscious internal action when the individual is aware of it. He's also aware that he has a variety of options in this position, but he stays silent since he doesn't believe he has the authority to change it. The employee's level of comprehension and acceptance, which is regarded part of their commitment, demonstrates this. Employee indifference can be detrimental to a company since it causes workers to lose interest in their jobs. Uninterested personnel are uninterested in the values of

their firm, which can lead to bad performance. As a result, an unrecognized employee costs the company and its employees a significant amount of money (Deniz, 2013).

Noise reduction among employees is still a relatively new notion. It occurs when employees fail to give critical information about their employers, whether purposefully or unintentionally. When employees refuse to speak with supervisors or managers, this can happen. Employees are frequently forced to choose whether or not to share their ideas, opinions, and perspectives at work. When they are unfrozen in ely, they usually choose the safe option of quiet, repressing facts that others would find valuable or thoughts that they wish they could convey (Fapohunda, 2016).

Organizational noiselessness refers to the absence of noise in the workplace.

Many management academics and experts have attempted to define organizational noiselessness using a variety of models, each based on his or her own personal opinion and viewpoint on the matter. Without going into too much depth, we'll deal with a few of the specific in that are pertinent to our research. The deliberate withholding of inquiries, remarks, and data by employees in Corning issues their work or company is known as organizational noiselessness. Employees' incapacity to communicate with one another, as well as their resistance to discussing work-related issues and topics, are considered as indicators (Alheet et al., 2019). It's also known as the practice of employees withholding information that could be advantageous or profitable to their employers (Fapohunda et al., 2016). We can use the aforementioned definite to go to a procedural definitive of organizational noiselessness to further our current investigation. Organizational noiselessness happens when an individual avoids or refuses to address personal difficulties at work for fear of being misinterpreted by his supervisor, resulting in strained relationships among his coworkers. "A collective phenomenon in which personnel conceal their ideas and concerns about future organizational issues," according to another definition of organizational noiselessness (Alqarni, 2020).

There are numerous factors that contribute to the lack of noise in the workplace.

Many experts have tried to pinpoint the causes of organizational noiselessness, emphasizing the phenomenon's negative consequences for the organization and its employees, which include hampered and delayed communication as well as poor organizational performance. Employees' continuous learning, abilities, and competencies, as well as mutually beneficial outcomes for both individuals and the firm, are emphasized in new management practices. In reality, the organizational voice has the potential to be a tremendous driver of change.

Employees, despite their confidence, are cautious to express their ideas, according to polls. They are afraid that speaking freely and participating in debates may put them in danger. As a result, the vast majority of employees are hesitant to raise their voices. At this point, the concept of organizational noiselessness (Erigüç et al., 2014) comes into play.

Employees become less interested about the quality of their work when innovation ceases, ethics deteriorates, and substandard products become more frequent. As a result, silence in the workplace is harmful to employees, the firm as a whole, and individuals. According to some,

the most typical and widespread factors are workplace climate, corporate culture, unjust treatment, lack of confidence, lack of experience, bias, fear of solitude, and weakened relationships (Jalilian & B in mani, 2014; Wynen et al., 2019). As a result, depending on the instrument we used, the research environment, and the sample size, we looked into four of those criteria:

1- Fear of jeopardizing the safety of ships

Staff are aware that the organization's structure and processes are flawed, but they are hesitant to express their concerns and suggestions for fear of being ignored on the one hand, or of losing their coworker relationships on the other (Moris in, 2014).

2. Workplace relationships in ed c in cerns

Some employees deliberately avoid raising their issues for fear of being characterized as troublemakers, which could result in them losing promotions or being treated unfairly by senior management. As a result, many prefer to remain silent (Gulluce et al., 2016).

3. Management and organizational reasons

These are usually associated with the company's decision-making process, in which management is unable to make sound decisions, resulting in decreased organizational effectiveness and bad performance. Employee apathy leads to these unfavorable results because they avoid debating or discussing issues for fear of engaging in sequences that they perceive will result in negative reactions (Jalilian & B in mani, 2014).

4. A lack of self-confidence

A person's ability to express himself without fear or reluctance is determined by his level of self-esteem. People with poor self-esteem are more likely to defend themselves. Speaking openly can sometimes bring out the best in us, but it can also have negative consequences if we don't succeed. Because they are fearful of taking risks, people with low self-esteem avoid expressing themselves and sharing their opinions (Akin & Ulusoy, 2016).

2.2. Possibility of gaining a market competitive advantage

The business world nowadays is extremely competitive. Starting a business is now easier and less expensive thanks to technological advancements that allow businesses to transfer their operations online and attract international customers in foreign marketplaces. The rise of online retail is a good example of this. In truth, all of this activity and competition makes standing out much more difficult. Creating a prospective Marketpriority is the most effective approach to distinguish oneself from the competition. Identifying the prospective Marketpriority is critical to the success of any firm. It's the force that allows a business to achieve greater focus, more sales, larger profit margins, and better customer and employee retention than its competitors.

Potential Market Priority—what buyers look for when evaluating a purchase—is a crucial determinant of long-term business value. The firm, its future, and profitability will be compromised if there is no plausible Market advantage (Peskest, 2018)

In the face of possible competitors who are unable to replicate those benefits in any way, market priority is defined as the ability to protect benefits and deploy distinctive value-generating tactics (Alalie, 2018). Furthermore, the long-term viability of medium and small firms is dependent on potential performance (Haseeb et al., 2019). After reviewing some of the concepts these researchers addressed in relation to potential Market advantage, it is clear that, despite their differing perspectives, they are simply emphasizing that it is the ability to meet the requirements of the clients dealing with it or looking in it by increasing its market share, exploiting its internal resources in the right direction, or the unique characteristics it possesses compared to others by increasing its market share, expatriating its internal resources in the right direction, or the unique characteristics it possesses compared to others by increasing its market share. As a result of these variables, it is feasible to assert that the potential Market priority is the greatest level of innovation and quality that separates the organization from its competitors through the intelligent use of limited resources, ensuring its survival and development.

According to Michael Porter, companies can gain a potential Market advantage by implementing three main strategies, which will be employed as dimensions in the current study to quantify the potential Market advantage. The strategies are as follows:

2.2.1. Strategic cost leadership is keeping a product's or service's expenses to a bare minimum while maintaining its quality. To get the most out of the organization's resources, this can be accomplished via boosting employee experience and growth. That is, in addition to emphasizing product in efficiency in a way that achieves the highest levels of productivity, the lowest possible costs, and the investment of machinery and manufacturing capabilities with the highest levels of product in capabilities and the lowest possible costs, whether in terms of product in scale, expenditures, or advertisements for after-sale service, To put it another way, it's a strategic need that forces a company to produce the cheapest product possible in order to earn above-average profits, hence growing its Market capabilities. The purpose of cost leadership is to achieve cost primacy by producing goods and services at a lower cost than competitors. To gain cost priority, companies could utilize a combination of forward, backward, and horizontal tactics (Kaliappen & Hilman, 2016).

2.2.2. Product placement that is well-thought-out

The firm can charge a higher price and enhance its market share by adapting a product or service to match a customer's specific needs. When a corporation gives unique or higher value to a customer through product quality, features, or after-sales support, the strategy is effective. Quality might be genuine or imagined, depending on the fashion, brand name, or image used. Product quality, delivery methods, service quality, and distribution networks can all be used to justify higher prices for companies who adopt a strategic approach to product creation. The strategy focuses on customers who seek a one-of-a-kind product and are willing to pay a premium for it (Kaliappen & Hilman, 2016).

Table (1): The descriptive statistics of the dimensions of "organizational noiselessness"

No.	Descriptive statistics tools Item	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Scale of response	Relative importance
a. Fear of undermining relationships						
1	I keep quiet out of fear of losing favor with my immediate superior.	3.3836	1.138	0.336	moderate	3
2	My colleagues have a unfavorable opinion of me when I talk about a question.	2.5890	1.152	0.445	low	4
3	I'm afraid that if I raise a question, my colleagues will not support me.	3.2466	1.051	0.323	moderate	2
4	If I talk about questions, it could affect my relationship with others.	3.6438	0.977	0.268	high	1
Overall mean of the dimension		3.2158	0.764	0.237	moderate	
b. Work-related concerns						
1	I'm afraid of losing my job or my position, thus I'm afraid to ask or raise a question..	3.3973	1.163	0.342	moderate	2
2	I am reluctant to raise any issue for fear of hindering and retaliation by direct superiors.	3.4658	1.014	0.292	high	1
3	I am object to abuse and oppression as a result of speaking about a question.	2.9452	1.078	0.366	moderate	4
4	Talking about a question may affect my position.	3.1370	1.109	0.353	moderate	3
Overall mean of the dimension		3.2363	0.714	0.220	moderate	
c. Organizational and management cause						
1	There is no official process in place in the company that permits us to discuss issues.	3.2329	1.034	0.319	moderate	2
2	The work environment here does not allow for freedom of expression.	3.1096	1.021	0.328	moderate	3
3	I am unable to convey my opinions due to the current structure.	3.0000	1.027	0.342	moderate	4
4	I don't discuss my concerns since I don't have faith in my managers.	3.1507	0.923	0.292	moderate	1
Overall mean of the dimension		3.1233	0.772	0.247	moderate	
d. Low self-esteem						
1	Workplace and work-related issues are not part of my expertise.	3.3699	0.905	0.268	moderate	1
2	Because of my low-paying employment, my thoughts are unimportant.	3.2466	0.939	0.289	moderate	3
3	I am unable to communicate at work due to a lack of experience.	3.3973	0.982	0.289	moderate	2
4	I lack the necessary experience to draft a proposal or ask a question.	3.2055	0.971	0.302	moderate	4
Overall mean of the dimension		3.3048	0.669	0.202	moderate	

According to the results of the descriptive analysis of the dimensions of dread of undermining relationship in Table, this is the fourth item (1). (If I discuss questions, it may have an impact on my relationships with others.) Have the highest arithmetic mean (3.6438) and the lowest standard deviation when compared to the rest of the elements in that dimension (0.977). These findings were reflected in a drop in the coefficient of variation (.268), placing it first in terms of relative relevance to the other dimensions and resulting in a high response scale. All of these data show that the sample's members agree on the topic's importance. In comparison to the other items, the second item (My colleagues have a negative opinion of me when I discuss a question.) has the lowest arithmetic mean (2.589) and the largest standard deviation in the dimension (1.152). As a result of the relative reduction in the

arithmetic mean and the resp in se scale, it ranked fourth in terms of relative importance, with a coefficient of vari in I in the arithmetic mean and the resp in se scale (.445). The overall mean of the dimensi in (Fear of undermining rel in I in ships) is (3.2158), and the standard devi in I in is (3.2158), as indicated by the coefficient of vari in I in that is (3.2158). (0.764). (0.237). This refers to the organizational silence demonstrated by the high scale of staff responses to the item, which represents the fear of losing favor with direct superiors and the dread of colleagues' bad attitudes and lack of support when discussing a work-related issue.

The sec in d item (I am afraid to voice any issue for fear of h in red and retaliation in I in by direct superiors.) has the highest arithmetic mean (3.4658) and the lowest standard devi in I in (1.014), which is the lowest compared to the other items. The arithmetic means, standard deviations in I in s, and coefficients of variation in I in s all fluctuated in the same way, as indicated in the table; the overall mean of the dimensi in is (3.2363), with a standard deviation in I in (0.714), and a coefficient of variation in I in s. (0.220). As the title suggests, these figures reveal the scope of the organizational noiselessness problem.

The results of the resp in ses of the sample members in rel in I in to the item of that dimensi in were equivalent for the third reason for organizational noiselessness, management and organizational cause. The standard deviation is (0.772), while the coefficient of variation is (3.1233). (0.247). this demonstrates that the example notion is in agreement with the item's importance in management and organizational reasons. The lack of a formal environment in which employees can communicate their opinions and ideas, as well as the hierarchy that inhibits them from doing so, as well as the employees' lack of faith in management, are all factors.

Finally, the data from the same table was used to figure out what was causing the low self-esteem. The dimensi average is 3.3048, the standard deviation is (0.669), and the coefficient of variance is (0.202). Tization a similar vein, the statistics show that the members of the sample agree on the concept of poor self-esteem when it comes to the item of the dimensi in of low self-esteem. These factors point to a lack of options as well as the employee's lack of experience, all of which make him hesitant to express his thoughts and ideas to his superiors. As a result, workplace noise levels have dropped.

2. Possible Market Priority

That changeable c consisted of three primary dimensions (cost leadership strategic, product strategic, and focus strategic). The following table shows the results of the descriptive statistics analysis, which are subsequently described below:

Table (2): The descriptive statistics of the dimensions of "possible Market advantage"

No.	Descriptive statistics tools-Item	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Scale of response	Relative importance
a. Cost leadership strategic						
1	Our company puts a lot of effort into enhancing worker productivity so that we may cut expenses while also protecting the environment and mental health.	3.5751	0.918	0.298	moderate	2
2	Our corporation is concerned with controlling expenses in order to save money continuously.	3.0000	1.130	0.376	moderate	5
3	Our business relies on achieving price benefits in order to cut costs while providing the best possible service.	2.8630	1.004	0.350	moderate	3
4	Our corporation depends on product innovation to save the costs of innovation.	2.7671	0.993	0.358	moderate	4
5	Our business relies on high-volume technology and resource allocation that is optimized.	3.0685	1.004	0.327	moderate	1
	Overall mean of the dimension	2.9699	0.685	0.230	moderate	
b. Product strategic						
1	Our corporation has accurate inspection and control devices that prevent errors.	3.3562	0.903	0.269	moderate	2
2	Our company is always entering new markets that are harder to penetrate for competitors.	3.2329	0.935	0.289	moderate	4
3	Our company offers high-quality items that ensure the retention of current clients as well as the acquisition of new ones.	3.1507	0.793	0.251	moderate	1
4	Our corporation has very advanced product technologies and is better than its competitors.	3.4247	0.956	0.279	high	3
5	Our company is always developing new formulae and technology to differentiate its products from those of competitors.	3.2603	0.957	0.293	moderate	5
	Overall mean of the dimension	3.2849	0.629	0.191	moderate	
c. Focus strategic						
1	Our business has a unique ability to penetrate a specific target market with safe items.	3.7123	0.935	0.251	high	1
2	Our corporation focuses on marketing its products in specific markets.	3.0548	1.153	0.377	moderate	5
3	Our corporation's systems are more impactful for a specific market when they penetrate targeted markets with clean products.	3.1233	0.881	0.282	moderate	2
4	Our corporation has the ability to control costs when serving specific customers.	3.5753	1.053	0.294	high	3
5	Our corporation adopts excellence philosophy by penetrating a specific market segment.	2.7671	0.950	0.343	moderate	4
	Overall mean of the dimension	3.2466	0.692	0.213	moderate	

Strategic cost leadership, product strategic leadership, and strategic focus were the three approaches that made up the adaptive framework. The results, as well as their scale based on the responses of the sample members, are shown in Table 1. (2). In terms of the corporation's tendency to imitate in e products in order to save costs of innovation, the first item has the highest arithmetic mean (3.5751) and the lowest arithmetic mean (0.298), and the in e rel in ed to compete has the lowest arithmetic mean in terms of the corporation's tendency to imitate in e products in order to save costs of innovation. It has a 2.7671 arithmetic mean, a 0.993 standard deviation, and a 2.7671 coefficient of variation. (0.993). (0.385).

The arithmetic mean of the strategic product is 3.2849, the standard deviation is (0.629), and the coefficient of variance is (0.191), showing that the sample's opinions on that dimension are in accord.

Finally, it is clear that the sample members' employment experience in firms is primarily strategic. The arithmetic mean of this approach is 3.2466, the standard deviation in I is (0.962), and the coefficient of variation in I is (0.213). This, in addition to the previous item's failure, illustrates the corporation's inadequate adoption of an excellence attitude by entering a certain market area, as shown in the table above.

In order to analyze the presumed correlations between the dimensions of the independent mutable on the one hand and the influence of the dependent mutable on the other, a correlation matrix is generated for the dimensions of the mutables, as shown in Table (2). The correlation coefficients were not exceptionally high, with the exception of a few instances (0.70). There is no multicollinearity between the components in businesses. Furthermore, the relationship between organizational noiselessness and enterprise potential Market advantage was inverse, with all correlation coefficients being negative. Then, after examining the research hypotheses with numerous regression models, those relationships are tested in their inferential framework.

Table (3): Correlation matrix of the dimensions of the research mutables

7	6	5	4	3	2	1		Dimensions
-0.567**	-0.648**	-0.682**	-0.633**	-0.691**	-0.554**	1	Pears in Correlation	Fear of undermining relationships
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		Sig. (2-tailed)	
-0.674**	-0.603**	-0.577**	-0.597**	-0.550**	1	0.554**	Pears in Correlation	Work-related concerns
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	Sig. (2-tailed)	
-0.665**	-0.724**	-0.838**	-0.710**	1	-0.550**	-0.691**	Pears in Correlation	Management and organizational cause
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	Sig. (2-tailed)	
-0.643**	-0.964**	-0.700**	1	-0.710**	-0.597**	-0.633**	Pears in Correlation	Low self-esteem
0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	Sig. (2-tailed)	
-0.632**	-0.719**	1	-0.700**	-0.838**	-0.577**	-0.682**	Pears in Correlation	Cost leadership strategic
0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Sig. (2-tailed)	
-0.642**	1	-0.719**	-0.964**	-0.724**	-0.603**	-0.648**	Pears in Correlation	Product strategic
0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Sig. (2-tailed)	
1	-0.642**	-0.632**	-0.643**	-0.665**	-0.674**	-0.567**	Pears in Correlation	Focus strategic
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Sig. (2-tailed)	

Table (3) shows the results of testing the research hypotheses as follows:

1- Regarding the first assumption that there is a significant inverse correlation between the causes of organizational noiselessness (fear of undermining

2- For the second assumption, that there is an important inverse correlation between the causes of organizational noiselessness and the cost leadership strategic, the correlation coefficients shown in Table (3) support the validity of the assumption, with correlation coefficients of (0.682), (-0.577), and (-0.3- For the third assumption, that there is an important inverse correlation between the causes of organizational noiselessness and the cost leadership strategic, the correlation coefficients shown in Table (3) support the validity of the assumption, with

correlation coefficients of (0.682), (-0.964). These findings suggest that a lack of organizational noise has a negative influence on a company's prospective market advantage.

3- Finally, the results in the table above support the third hypothesis that there is a significant negative link between organizational noiselessness and the dependent component, i.e. prospective Market advantage, which is represented here by strategic emphasis. The results were (0.567), (0.674), (-0.665), and (0.643) for organizational noiselessness and strategic focus, respectively. The above findings back up the research hypotheses and demonstrate that organizational noise reduces the potential market advantage.

These findings can be corroborated by utilizing the regression coefficient to test further hypotheses about the detrimental impact of organizational noiselessness and projected Market priority characteristics. To test their predictions concerning the effect of organizational noiselessness and its dimensions in the predicted Market priority and its dimensions, the researchers used the regression coefficient as shown in Table. (4).

Table (4): Results of testing the research hypotheses						
Sign. scale	F-test	Coeff. of def.	Sign. scale	t-test	Parameters	Statistical results
P>F	F	R ²	P> t	t	B	Details
.000	48.64	0.74	.046	2.06-	.13	Fear of undermining relationships in ships → Cost leadership strategic
			.135	-1.31	.09	Work-related concerns → Cost leadership strategic
			.000	-4.06	.60	Management and organizational cause → Cost leadership strategic
			.039	2.27-	.14	Low self-esteem → Cost leadership strategic
.000	237.3	0.93	.491	0.962-	.03	Fear of undermining relationships in ships → Product strategic
			.533	1.23-	.02	Work-related concerns → Product strategic
			.050	1.97-	.06	Management and organizational cause → Product strategic
			.000	5.12-	.89	Low self-esteem → Product strategic
.000	24.81	0.59	0.514	0.942-	.03	Fear of undermining relationships in ships → Focus strategic
			0.00	3.89-	.38	Work-related concerns → Focus strategic
			0.15	2.29-	.31	Management and organizational cause → Focus strategic
			.047	1.99-	-.18	Low self-esteem → Focus strategic

The following is the initial sub-assumption: Table (4) shows that all variables of organizational noiselessness are important in the cost leadership strategic, which is the first dimension of the dependent variable, i.e. the potential Market advantage. The beta coefficients for the dimensions of fear of undermining relationships in ships (= .13, P = 0.046), management and organizational causes that have a strategic impact (= .60, P = 0.000), and low self-esteem, excluding the dimension of work-related concerns (= .14, P = 0.039) are (= .60, P = 0.000). Because of the coefficient of determination, the model's total explanatory power is (R² = .74), which is extremely significant (P = 0.000). In the investigated organization, the organizational noiselessness changeable dimensions and their relevant dimensions explain 74 percent of the variance. Other factors that could aid interpretation had a considerable impact on the remaining (26%), but they were not included in the test model. The impact of the organizational noiselessness dimension on the strategic product is similar, as indicated by the R² = 0.93 in the

same table, indicating that the organizational noiselessness dimension explains a large amount of variation (93 percent). Other factors that were not considered in the test model will almost certainly have an impact on the remaining 7%. Finally, as evidenced by the significant negative association, the organizational noiselessness component has an impact on strategic attention. The difference in organizational noiselessness, as measured by the dimensions, is depicted here (59 percent). Other variables that were not considered in the test model are likely to have an impact on the remaining 41%.

4. Conclusion

Following is a summary of the most important conclusions that arose from that analysis in light of the evaluation of the research's practical framework:

- 1- Most items' arithmetic means exceeded the study sample's arithmetic means, illustrating the enormous scale of dimensions of the research mutables, i.e. organizational noiselessness and projected Market advantage (3).
- 2- The findings supported the research's hypothesis that there is an adverse relationship between organizational noiselessness and expected market advantage.
- 3- The results also demonstrated that organizational noiselessness has a detrimental impact on potential Market advantage, as shown by the regression in the two mutables study.

4.1. Don't forget to include a "I" in your suggestion.

Based on the outcomes of the practical examination of each variable as indicated in the corresponding tables, the most important recommendations in this study are as follows:

- 1- It's vital to focus on employee performance by allowing them to express themselves through active communication and the creation of a flexible organizational structure that allows subordinates and leaders to communicate effectively.
- 2- Increasing employee confidence and encouraging them to speak up about their ideas and problems in a non-disruptive manner.
- 3- Giving employees some autonomy and decision-making ability while also giving them the necessary authority, reducing isolation and, as a result, organizational noiselessness.
- 4- Continuing to provide seminars for managers and employees to break down barriers, build a strong team spirit, and encourage collaboration in order to gain a competitive advantage.
- 5- Working to encourage staff to react to enquiries in a professional and business-friendly manner.

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